

Non-toxic wood binders: Challenges and Future opportunities - A Perspective.

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Abstract

Most of the wood adhesives used in industries are synthetic and carcinogenic because of the formaldehyde emission that occurs during the manufacturing process and their usage by the general public. Furthermore, the re-manufacturability of synthetic wood adhesive used products such as particleboard is limited. This causes waste accumulation which ends up in the landfill. Synthetic wood adhesives are mostly derived from depleting petrochemical resources. Therefore, introducing bio-based wood adhesives would be the best alternative way to overcome these issues. Agricultural and industrial by-products can be used as raw materials for most bio-based wood adhesives and additives. In addition, the ability to blend bio-based adhesives with the synthetic ones makes the adaptation to the current manufacturing lines of wood panel production easier. It has also been shown that the addition of nanoparticle into bio-based adhesive resins gives added advantages on their performance. Many of the bio-based wood adhesive formulations have demonstrated to satisfy international industrial standards in most of their physical and mechanical properties. However, in general, the moisture adsorption and the commonly poor water-resistance of wood-based panels manufactured using bio-based adhesives have to be improved.

Keywords: Bio-based adhesive, Formaldehyde emission, Engineered wood panels.

1 Introduction

Currently, the most widely used industrial wood adhesives are aldehyde yielding compounds such as melamine-formaldehyde (MF), melamine urea-formaldehyde (MUF), phenol-formaldehyde (PF) and urea-formaldehyde (UF) resins (so-called amino-plastic resins) [1]. However, it is now recognised that these adhesives emit formaldehyde. The effect of formaldehyde emission was re-classified from “probable human carcinogen” to “known human carcinogen” by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) in 2004 [2], [3]. Apart from that, petroleum-based wood adhesives may not be biodegradable. This can lead to waste accumulation [4]. On the other hand, bio-sourced wood adhesives are renewable, recyclable, re-manufacturable, natural and non-oil-derived materials. UF as a non-bio-based adhesive, can actually be

sourced from a non-oil derived raw material and it is most used (90%) to manufacture engineered wood panels used in households [5]. Tannins, lignin, carbohydrates, unsaturated oils, proteins, blood and collagen are bio-based wood adhesives that were utilised in the past, before the introduction of toxic synthetic wood adhesives [6].

The wood adhesive industry is about two thirds (by volume) of all the adhesives used in the world. Each year, 11 million tons of UF resins are being sold [7].

Polymeric 4,4'-Methylene diphenyl isocyanate (pMDI) and 4,4'-Methylene diphenyl isocyanates (MDI) are widely used in the wood adhesive industry. They show high bonding strength, short press time, resistance to water and 0% emission of formaldehyde compared to the traditional water-based urea-formaldehyde resins and phenol-formaldehyde. The main issue of pMDI is its high price [8], even though it is highly efficient (small amount needed to achieve product with optimal performance), has good weather resistance and fast curing [9], [10].

1.1 Formaldehyde emission - (FE)

The annual global production of formaldehyde is approximately 29 million tons [11]. International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has determined with sufficient evidence that formaldehyde causes nasopharyngeal cancer in human beings [12]. FE is released both by the adhesives and by the wood itself [13]. The formaldehyde emission is influenced by exogenous factors and endogenous factors as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 : Factors affecting on formaldehyde emission [26, 27].

Exogenous factors	Endogenous factors
Air humidity	Wood species
Temperature	Type of resins used
Air change	Condition of manufacture

The formaldehyde emission is mainly generated by three sources.

1. Formaldehyde compound in the wood material,
2. Residual free formaldehyde of the formaldehyde-based adhesive that is not involved in the reaction (The main source of indoor air pollution), and
3. Formaldehyde released by the structural degradation of the wood-based panel used [14].

The FE can be measured by desiccator method [15], gas analysis method (UNI EN717-2:1996) and chamber method (UNI EN717-1:2004) [16]–[18].

1.1.1 Reducing FE

Synthetic wood adhesive resins can be modified to reduce or minimise FE without degrading mechanical and physical properties of wood-based panels. FE can be reduced by adding formaldehyde scavengers or by decreasing free formaldehyde in the adhesive [8]. Urea can be taken as the most typical formaldehyde scavengers used in wood adhesive industry in addition to ammonia and ammonium salts [19]. Charcoal (the best scavenger out of all), wheat flour and tannin powder are organic scavengers. The

formaldehyde emission can be reduced by 40% by using 5% (wt.) of charcoal [20][21]. Activated multi-walled carbon nanotubes, carbon nanotubes, and exfoliated graphite nanoparticles behave as formaldehyde absorbent in formaldehyde-based adhesives [22], [23]. Formaldehyde emission can be reduced by adding diphenylmethane-4, 4'-diisocyanate (MDI) into the UF resin mixture [24]. The hardener type associated in particleboards significantly affects the formaldehyde emission [5]. Compounds, that can be added to synthetic adhesives as hardeners for particleboards production, have shown to significantly affect the formaldehyde emission [25]. Nevertheless, when magnesium chloride was added to the resin as a hardener, it seemed to emit more formaldehyde, as shown in Figure 1, even though it showed the best mechanical properties [5].

Figure 1 : Formaldehyde emission with hardener type used in engineered wood panels [5].

Citric and oxalic acid, in solid form, were used as catalysts in UF resin in the production of particleboard to enhance the internal bond strength and to reduce the formaldehyde emission [25].

Non-volatile and non-toxic aldehyde glyoxal was reacted with melamine to prepare novel melamine-glyoxal resins to eliminate the formaldehyde emission from melamine resin [26]. Formaldehyde emission can also be reduced by adding furfural into UF resin [27]. Aluminium sulphate and ammonium persulphate have been shown to reduce free formaldehyde (uncombine monomeric formaldehyde) in adhesives by 20.0% and 60.0% respectively [28]. Diatomaceous earth as an inorganic additive can be used to reduce the FE by 45% following addition to the UF resin [29].

Inorganic ammonium salts such as ammonium chloride, ammonium phosphate, ammonium hydrogen phosphate, ammonium sulphate and persulphate can be used to reduce free formaldehyde by acting as accelerators in the resin cross-linking process. Organic additives such as polyvinyl alcohol, polyacrylamide, starch, urea, and melamine

can reduce FE from UF-based adhesives, by acting as formaldehyde scavengers [30]. Moreover, the FE can also be minimised by changing the manufacturing conditions that lead to change the physical and mechanical properties of engineered wood panels [31].

To reduce FE in indoor environment, techniques such as avoiding and removing the formaldehyde sources, surface coating, increasing ventilation, fumigation with ammonia, catalytic reactions and adsorption can be adopted [32].

1.2 Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) emission

VOCs are emitted from natural sources and manufactured products. They are in the gaseous phase at room temperature due to their vapour pressures [33]. Solid wood, engineered wood-based panels, flooring products, paints, finishes, sealants, waxes, adhesives, mastics, cements, roofing materials, furniture, insulations and cleaning products emit VOCs [34]. The VOCs emitted by wood and wood-based panels are α -pinene, β -pinene, camphene Δ^3 -carene, limonene, benzaldehyde, decanal, furfural, hexanal, nonanal, octanal, pentanal, acetic acid and formaldehyde [35]. Most of those are emitted from indoor applications. Humans spend 90% of their lives indoors [36]. VOCs emission in newly renovated homes is much higher than the average homes [37]. As a result of this, humans are vulnerable to health risk associated with inhalation of VOCs emission. Therefore, the construction materials have to be selected considering indoor air quality as the main criteria [38].

Wood and wood-based panels release non-formaldehyde VOCs and formaldehyde related VOCs [39]. Possible formaldehyde related VOC emissions from wood-based materials can be categorised as shown in Figure 2. Synthetic adhesives such as PF, PVA, epoxy and polyurethane consist of toxic chemicals namely as epichlorohydrin, MDI, TDI, formaldehyde that are harmful for the health of living organisms and the environment [40].

Figure 2 : Possible VOC emissions related to formaldehyde for the case of a wood-based material [32].

Incorporating bio-based adhesive formulations into the existing manufacturing routes as shown in Figure 3 would reduce formaldehyde and VOC emissions of the final wood-based panels. The mixing of bio-adhesives with additives and mixing of the adhesive formulation with liquid chemical or water should be done 'in-situ' as the storage life of bio-based adhesives are comparatively longer than that of synthetic adhesives in the adaptation process. As a result of incorporating bio-based wood adhesives, the hot press time should be increased due to the increase in press factor as shown in Eq. 1. Most of the bio-based and non-toxic wood adhesives that can be used directly or blended with synthetic wood adhesives are mentioned in this study.

$$Press\ Factor = \frac{Time\ (s)}{Thickness\ (mm)} \quad (1)$$

Figure 3 : Incorporating bio-based wood adhesive formulations (in brown) into existing production lines (in black) of wood-based panels that synthetic adhesives are used.

2 Wheat gluten adhesives

Gluten proteins can be considered as the most complex proteins network in nature [41]. Wheat gluten (WG) is a relatively inexpensive abundant protein source [42] and a by-product of starch production to obtain bioethanol. WG is a complex mixture containing 80% wheat protein, and the rest is lipids, polysaccharides, and minerals [2], [43]. Wheat protein consists of glutenins that have elastic properties (being dispersible in acids) and gliadins that have viscous properties (soluble in alcohol) [2]. Gliadins are monomeric and have low molecular weight, while glutenins are polymeric and have high molecular weight [44]. WG has an isoelectric point of 7.3 with a high amount of hydrophobic amino acids [45]. As a result of that, WG is not dispersible in water alone, but it becomes so following the addition of alkali and acids [2]. WG-based adhesives can be prepared by dispersing WG powder in an alkaline solution. When a mixture of 25 wt.% WG with 0.2M NaOH applied to make wood panels, was heated at 130°C for 15 minutes under a pressure of 0.7 MPa, it was able to provide the highest bond strength of 7.07 MPa and the optimum bond line thickness compared to the other percentages of WG and NaOH that were tested [46]. Dispersion concentration, the viscosity, and the application method were the factors strongly affecting WG dispersion into the wood particles. Nevertheless, other factors such as drying temperature, presence of cross-linkers, dispersing agent and type of wood species had less effect on the penetration and film formation [47]. Performing the WG dispersion in two steps, by drying the glued chips in-between the first and the second addition was beneficial compared to other proposed one-step processes [45].

WG (80%) was mixed with UF resin (20%) and boric acid (1% and 2%) was added as a fungicide was added to the resin mixture and used to produce high-density particleboard using reed instead of wood particles. Addition of boric acid resulted in no significant change in the mechanical properties such as modulus of rupture (MOR), modulus of elasticity (MOE), internal bond (IB) strength, but a slight improvement in the physical properties such as water absorption and thickness swelling was observed [48]. The particle size of alkali-denatured WG in WG-protein adhesives is independent of the tensile strength achieved [49]. The adhesive performance of wheat protein thermoset resins was enhanced by adding triacetin [50]. Wheat gluten hydrolysed (0.3%–0.6%), heat-treated at 90°C and finally dispersed in solution of 0.1 M NaOH(aq) was used as

wood adhesives. The result shows improved bond strength and an enhanced water-resistance [51].

Wheat gluten itself has shown better wood adhesive properties when mixed with alkaline such as NaOH. It can also be blended with synthetic adhesive such as UF in an acidic environment to minimise the formaldehyde emission.

3 Sodium alginate

The basic raw material for the production of sodium alginate (SA) is brown algae [52]. Alginates are unbranched polysaccharides and complex carbohydrate polymers derived from brown seaweeds [53]. Tens of million tons (frozen weight) of seaweeds are harvested from offshore and onshore [54]. Alginates are used in industrial applications because of their properties of gelling, viscosifying and stabilising [55]. SA has been used as a biodegradable additive in the papermaking industry with polyamideamine-epichlorohydrin to increase the mechanical properties of the cycles fibres [56]. SA is usually blended or modified or copolymerised with other biopolymers in order to be used as a structural scaffold [57]. The chemical structure of SA depicted in Figure 4, shows the phenolic polymer nature and the ability to react with wood cell wall hydroxyl groups when SA is dissolved in water.

Figure 4 : Chemical structure of sodium alginate molecule [57], [58].

It has been reported that aldehyde sodium alginate and amino gelatin can be utilised in surgeries as a bioadhesive for soft tissue [59]. Sodium alginate also demonstrated to have the best bioadhesive force among the bioadhesive polymers tested for the production of omeprazole buccal adhesive tablet [60], [61]. By mixing chitosan and sodium alginate, oral mucosal bioadhesive tablets of diltiazem were produced [62].

4 Lipid-based adhesives

Canola, soybean, palm, maize, sunflower, castor and jojoba seeds are mainly used in industrial applications for the extraction of their lipid/oil. The oils can be functionalised by transesterification, epoxidation, hydro formation and ozonisation to achieve enhanced functional properties [63]. Soy oil and castor oil [64] were previously used to make bio polyols to use in polyurethane wood adhesive.

5 Oil palm trunk-based wood adhesives

Carboxymethyl starch extracted from the oil palm trunk by using the method of Noor et al. [65] was tested as wood adhesives by comparing with native starch, UF and by mixing it with 2% of UF. The extracted carboxymethyl starch itself when used as an adhesive led to products with modulus of elasticity and internal bond strength satisfying the requirements of the Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS). The addition of 2% of UF allowed to obtain a modulus of rupture as 'Type 8 particleboard' in JIS [66].

Polyurethane wood adhesive prepared without adding volatile organic solvents from palm oil-based polyester polyol exhibited comparable mechanical strength to a PVAc wood adhesive available in the market [67]. The properties of synthesised polyol that included higher molecular weight, lower hydroxyl functionality, good spreadability on wood surfaces, strong lap shear strength and long gel time (90 min) implied that it can be used for adhering large wood surface with a longer working life [68].

Particle sizes of 0.5 mm, 1.0 mm and 2.0 mm of dried oil palm strands were used to make sample boards. The samples made from 2.0 mm particles of oil palm were able to meet the minimum requirement for the mechanical properties while other sizes show better properties [69].

Liquefied oil palm extracted from empty fruit bunches with phenol can be used as a novolak¹ resin in wood adhesives [70].

Lignocelluloses biomass bio-oil from oil palm trunk can be applied for wood preservation in industrial scale [71]–[77].

6 Protein Adhesives

Proteins are polymer chains made out of amino acids linked together by peptide bonds. Agricultural, industrial and forestry residuals and municipal wastes (disposed either by incineration or by landfilling [78], [79]) even consist of proteins, which are the principal organic building blocks in all living organisms. Proteins represent over 50% of the dry weight of a cell [80][81].

Single-cell protein extracted from yeast and used as an adhesive showed a joint strength from 2.40 MPa to 2.99 MPa proving as similar to the urea-formaldehyde wood adhesive but with superior performance [82]. Whey-protein based aqueous polymer-isocyanate adhesive reacts with polyvinyl alcohol and cross-linking agent polymeric methylene diphenyl di-isocyanate to produce a resin, which when used has led to wood products that have satisfied the demands for structural uses in JIS K6806-2003 standard [83]. Whey protein post-treated by phenol formaldehyde oligomers as wood adhesive showed good water-resistance. When these were combined with ammonia and sodium sulphite

¹ Novolaks (or novolacs) are PF resins with a formaldehyde to phenol molar ratio of less than one.

showed a positive effect on formaldehyde emission as these behave as formaldehyde scavengers [84].

Wood adhesive made from the protein extracted from *Rhodotorula rubra* with some reinforcing agents (liquid glyoxal in 40% concentration, resorcinol in flakes and liquid diphenylmethane diisocyanate) has given a good performance and stiffness, comparable to that using UF [82][85]. On the contrary, it has been shown that Zein (protein of maize) is not suitable as a wood adhesive at least in the tested gluing conditions such as glue quantity used measured in grams per square meter, spreading on each side of the assemblies, pressing time and the bonding pressure [86].

7 Canola protein isolated adhesives

Canola (vegetable oil derived from rapeseed) is the second-largest oilseed crop product after soy [87], [88]. Most of the canola protein is used as animal feed [43]. Canola meal is a by-product of canola oil extraction and contains between 30% and 50% of proteins [89]. Canola proteins were modified by using sodium bisulphite (NaHSO_3 , 3 g/l). This seemed to improve dramatically the flowability and handleability of the adhesive without compromising its wet shear strength [90], [91]. However, whereas NaHSO_3 did not seem to improve the adhesive properties of canola proteins [90], it was able to improve its water-resistance [91].

Another study has reported that polyurethane (PU) adhesives were produced using canola oil derived polyols and they demonstrated better adhesive properties in terms of lap shear strength than synthetic PU adhesives [92].

8 Soy-based adhesives

Soy-bean flour, soybean concentrate and soy-bean protein isolate (SPI) are cheaper [93] than some synthetic resins and have shown good mechanical properties when they are used as non-toxic wood adhesives [94]. Soybean proteins concentrate with gelatin resin showed increasing bond strengths in both shear and tensile modes [95]. Soy flour was used to make interior plywood from the 1930s to the 1960s [96]. It was gradually replaced by UF adhesives due to lower cost and rapid curing of UF under hot pressing conditions [97][98].

Soy protein isolate was modified with maleic anhydride and mixed with polyethylenimine in order to achieve dry shear strength of 7 MPa at hot-pressing time of 2 min [99]. Also, soy protein/ CaCO_3 hybrid wood glue seemed to improve greatly the water-resistance and bonding strength of soy protein adhesives by compacting rivets or interlocking links, and by ion crosslinking of calcium, carbonate and hydroxyl ions in the adhesive [100].

Water-resistance can also be improved by adding lignin-based resin into the soy-bean meal-based adhesive [101]. SPI has also shown a strong affinity to wood cellulose almost as twice as wheat gluten adhesives under acidic and alkaline conditions [102].

Some other adhesive proteins such as heat-cured or heat-set animal blood and casein have been blended with soy protein for bonding interior-grade plywood, doors, and millwork [103]. The moduli of rupture of soy-based adhesive (57.319 MPa) and petroleum-based urea-formaldehyde adhesive (38.12 MPa) were evaluated and

compared and the results indicated a better flexural strength of the soy-based adhesive for making plywood [104].

Glyoxalated soy flour adhesives for wood particleboard with a very small amount of glyoxalated lignin or tannin and without any addition of UF, PF, MUF were able to satisfy the relevant standard specifications for interior grade wood boards [105]. However, the major disadvantage of the soy-protein-based adhesives is their poor water-resistance [106]. This is mainly due to the weak intermolecular interactions that are easily destroyed by water, including hydrogen bonds, electrostatic bonds, Van der Waals forces, disulphide bonds (so-called an S-S bond, or disulphide bridge). The three major chemical modifications performed to enhance water-resistance of bio-adhesives can be classified into three categories: protein denaturing agent modification; soy protein molecular modification (graft modification, acetylated modification, protein enzyme modification, and bio-mimetic modification); and mixing with reactive cross-linkers [107]–[109]. The soy-based adhesive cross-linked with hydroxymethyl phenol cured at low temperature (80°C) showed better mechanical performance and heat resistance than the adhesive without hydroxymethyl phenol [110].

A wood adhesive prepared by cross-linking soy-bean soluble polysaccharide in soybean meal and then conjugating it with soy protein showed enhanced thermal and mechanical properties and reduced moisture absorption, meeting the water-resistance requirements for interior use plywood [111].

A long-chain cross-linker diethylene glycol diglycidyl ether and the denaturation agent sodium dodecyl sulphate have shown to increase the performance and water-resistance of soybean meal-based wood adhesive [112]. Soybean meal and triglycidylamine and modified sepiolite have also shown enhanced performance as wood adhesive [113].

Soybean meal with ethylene glycol diglycidyl ether and diethylenetriamine can be used as adhesive in the plywood industrial application [114].

Water-resistance of soy protein isolate adhesive was increased by introducing triglycidylamine and γ -(2,3-epoxypropoxy) propyltrimethoxysilane as a cross-linker [115].

Superior water-resistance and shear strength of plywood panels were achieved when polyethyleneimine and NaOH were added to the Soy-bean flour/acetic anhydride adhesive formulations [116].

A soy-based adhesive cross-linked with a hybrid cross-linker made of 6.4% of epoxy resin and 6.4% of melamine-formaldehyde showed the best water-resistance at a press temperature of 160°C and press time of 8 min among the several percentages of hybrid cross-linker tested [117].

Thermochemical treatment of soy-bean protein in the presence of sodium sulphite and sodium dodecyl sulphate, followed by cross-linking by epichlorohydrin-modified polyamide showed wet bond strength of up to 1.22 MPa, exceeding the required value for structural use of plywood (0.98 MPa) [118]. Processing pressure of soy-bean wood adhesive was found to be the most important factor in determining adhesion strength. The optimal value of that pressure was 4.55 MPa [119]. Soy-bean protein-acrylate composite mini-emulsions were used for wood adhesive showing an internal bond strength higher than 0.7 MPa, meeting the standard of GB/T9846-2004 II [120].

Chemical phosphorylation of soy flour, using phosphoryl chloride (POCl_3) as a phosphorylating agent, dramatically increased its wet bond strength from 1.06 MPa to 2.6 MPa [121]. The water-resistance of soy flour-based wood adhesives was greatly improved by adding POCl_3 and inorganic oxidising agents, such as NaClO_2 and $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_2)_2$. These oxidising agents are non-toxic and environmentally safe [122].

Soy flour with a curing agent derived from the reaction of epichlorohydrin and ammonium hydroxide in water was used as a wood adhesive with NaOH, showing an improved water-resistance as well as an improved dry shear strength [123].

Soy flour with polyamidoamine-epichlorohydrin as a wood adhesive showed greater adhesive bond with protein-protein and protein-wood [124].

Modification of defatted soy flour with acid salt and alkali showed a high water-resistance and a general high performance as a wood adhesive [125].

Soy flour crosslinked by 1,2,3,4-butanetetracarboxylic acid was used as high-performance environmentally friendly defatted soy flour-based bio-adhesives [126].

Enhanced water-resistance and bonding strength were achieved by using defatted soy flour enzymolyzed by Viscozyme L as a bio-based wood adhesive [81].

Rice husk (RH) as wood chips and soy-protein as the adhesive were chemically modified to increase the performance of formed medium-density particleboard. NaOH or NaOH and H_2O_2 were used to eliminate lignin, hemicellulose, and silica from RH by chemical treatment. Then alkali-treated soy-proteins adhesive was reacted with the treated RH. A better mechanical interlocking and more hydrogen bonding between OH groups of cellulose and the polar groups of the unfolded soy-proteins were responsible for greater adhesion strength [127].

Generally, soy-protein-based adhesives show poor water-resistance due to the water disruption of hydrogen bonds, electrostatic bonds, and disulphide bonds. Among all the tested methods to improve water-resistance of soy-protein based adhesives the following showed the most promising results:

- Addition of polyethyleneimine and NaOH,
- Bending with epoxy resin and melamine-formaldehyde,
- Addition of sodium sulphite and sodium dodecyl sulphate, followed by cross-linking by epichlorohydrin-modified polyamide,
- Reaction of epichlorohydrin and ammonium hydroxide in water and then with NaOH.

9 Natural Rubber-based wood Adhesive

The two types of natural rubber-based adhesives are:

1. Latex adhesives, made by adding stabilisers, wetting agents, and other components to natural rubber-based adhesives; and
2. Solution adhesives made by adding a solvent such as toluene, naphtha, or trichloroethane into natural rubber-based adhesives [128].

Modified natural rubber latex used as natural rubber-based wood adhesive had shown lower formaldehyde emission compared to commercial UF adhesive [129].

Epoxidised natural rubber-based wood adhesives (ENR) show superior properties compared with unmodified natural rubber-based adhesives [130]. Higher tensile strength was obtained by using ENR-toluene-based wood adhesive [131]. SEM images indicated better adhesion properties of modified natural rubber compared to the unmodified one [132]. Natural rubber is also used to produce cellulose acetate and cellulose acetate butyrate adhesives [133]. MOR and MOE values of composite boards made using natural rubber-wood adhesives were much higher than those of oil palm fronds and stem, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 : Bending Strength between compressed oil palm fronds composite boards, Composite Oil Palm Stem and Rubber-wood [134].

Composite boards	MOR (N/mm ²)	MOE (N/mm ²)
Oil Palm Fronds	16.66	999.61
Oil Palm Stem	15.13	480.06
Rubber-wood	56.57	2543.34

10 Chicken Feather Protein-Based Wood Adhesives

Chicken feathers are composed of 91% keratin protein. The insoluble feather keratin can be used to produce feedstuffs, fertilisers, glue and films [135]. Today, most of the proteinaceous material of waste feathers is landfilled [136]–[138]. On the other hand, proteinaceous adhesives such as chicken feather-based adhesive are being used in the wood-based panel industry by using hydrolysed chicken feather (in NaOH) and hydrolysed chicken blood (in H₂SO₄) as the hardener [139].

Using feather proteins as adhesives showed added advantages compared to soy protein due to the hydrophobic nature of keratin, which is the protein contained in chicken feathers. Anti-mildew nature of feather protein, the less likeliness to flocculate and the easier nature to hydrolyse as compared to globulin such as the one found in soy, show possibilities of manufacturing a better adhesive using feather protein [140]. Chicken feather fibre can have the ability to withstand both thermal and mechanical stress due to its high thermal energy [137]. Waste keratin material such as feather, hair or hoofs with known adhesives such as blood, casein, bone glue or hide glue, either alone or combined with other glues, has shown to be suitable to produce plywood, corrugated paper, cardboard and other similar materials [141]. The protein molecules in chicken feathers unfolded by heating in alkaline solution and after exposure to polar functional groups of wood veneers, showed an appreciable adhesion property under dry condition. However, the water-resistance of the resulting plywood panels was poor [79]. Improved water-resistance and reduced thickness swelling of medium density fibreboard (MDF) made using chicken feathers fibre and 5% of PF resin were achieved in comparison with the control panels due to the hydrophobic nature of keratin in the feather fibres [142], [143].

Improved stiffness of elastomeric matrix and increased storage modulus were found in a composite made using copolymer styrene-butadiene and chicken feathers [144].

Three proteins (soy-proteins, wheat gluten, and chicken feathers) were able to provide nearly the same cohesion to fibres and abrasion resistance as starch in the cotton warp sizing industry. This result indicates that soy-proteins and wheat gluten can be replaced by chicken feather to prepare different sizes cotton threads. This can save food by sparing wheat and soy, is environmentally friendly because of the use of a waste product and can also benefit the poultry and textile industries [145].

The hollow honeycomb structures and the very low density of chicken feather give excellent compressibility and resilience, warmth retention and fluid absorption properties for lightweight composites and sound protection applications [146]. Acoustic panels can be made using chicken feathers, cardboard bins glue, and water [147].

Chicken feather with wood pulp can be used in paper manufacturing industries by varying the proportion of the chicken feather fibres up to 100% wood pulp [148].

The hollow keratin fibres of the chicken feather can be used to make environmentally friendly composite by using soybean resin [149].

11 Citric acid as wood additive

Citric acid (CA) is used as the major component of adhesive formulation to manufacture wood-based moulding, fibreboards and particleboards [150]. A mixture of *Acacia mangium* bark powder and 20 wt.% of CA as the adhesive were hot-pressed at 180°C and 4 MPa for 10 minutes to make binderless boards. The results have shown good bending properties and good MOR and MOE [151]. Increasing CA content has shown an increased water-resistance [152]. Bamboo particleboard bonded with CA has shown high performance on mechanical properties, better dimensional stability [153] and excellent water-resistance. The internal bond value was increased by 10 times when 10 wt.% of CA was used for bonded boards. When the percentage was increased to 30% (wt.), the optimum MOR and MOE were obtained [154].

Water absorption and thickness swelling of three different bamboos (petung, wulung and apus) particleboard were reduced significantly when CA adhesive content was increased from 0% to 30% [155].

Particleboards adhesive made using CA and sucrose (15/85 and 10/90 wt.%) has shown higher mechanical properties, lower brittleness, and similar dimensional stability compared to the adhesives made using CA and PF [156]. Pre-dried wood particle bonded showed the best mechanical properties and water-resistance with 20%-30% (wt.) CA [157]. The optimal pressing temperature and time were 200°C and 10 min respectively [158].

CA can also be used as a wood adhesive additive, as a cross-linking catalyst, as a crosslinking agent or as a dispersing agent in order to enhance the adhesive strength [150].

Figure 5 Chemical structure of Citric acid.

According to the chemical structure of CA shown in Figure 5, hydroxyl groups of the wood cell wall can react with the hydroxyl groups of CA releasing H₂O (vapour) at high temperature. CA molecule can react with more than one wood cell, as it has more than one hydroxyl group, bonding one wood cell to the other chemically.

The use of CA adhesive can provide improved dimensional stability, enhanced water-resistance and can assure manufacture of particleboards with high performance mechanical properties [159].

12 Cotton-seed protein wood adhesives

Cotton is mainly grown for the fibre industry. Cottonseed consists of gossypol, which is toxic for human consumption [43]. Cotton-seed protein as a wood adhesive has shown higher shear strength compared to the modified or unmodified soy protein-based adhesives [160]. The adhesive properties of cottonseed are independent of the type of meal used (derived from glanded or glandless) and the method of fraction retentate (by water/NaCl and phosphate buffer/NaCl) [161].

Water washing of cottonseed meal is more cost-efficient and environmentally friendly compared to the alkaline extraction and acidic precipitation [162]. Alkali extraction and acid precipitation were done on defatted cottonseed to get cottonseed protein isolate. Cottonseed meal isolates, as well as the defatted cottonseed meal, can be used as wood adhesives. Water washed cottonseed meal showed better water-resistance properties compared to the defatted cottonseed meal [163].

Several protein modifiers such as amino acids, fatty acids, and other organic molecules with cationic or anionic charges were used in cottonseed and soy protein isolate-based wood adhesives. When compounds with anionic charges such as aspartic acid, glutamic acid, acetic acid, butyric acid, and adipic acid were used in the cotton-seed protein-based adhesives, these exhibited the best performance. However, there was no significant enhancement in properties on soy protein isolate [164].

Cottonseed protein isolate was used as a wood adhesive in the presence of protein denaturants, such as guanidine hydrochloride (GuHCl), sodium dodecyl sulfonate, urea,

and alkali. The dry adhesive strength and hot water-resistance of cotton-seed protein isolate was superior to that of soy protein isolate, with or without the denaturants used [165].

Cottonseed and soy protein isolates were separately blended with a polysaccharide such as starch, xylan, cellulose. Blended cottonseed protein has shown superior adhesive strength compared to the soy protein in the protein/polysaccharide blends [166].

The phosphorus-containing additives have shown to improve the hot water-resistance of the cottonseed protein formulations but showed no effect on the soy protein formulations [167]. Dry and water-soaked bonding strengths of pure UF resins were improved by introducing 30% of cottonseed meal. It also improved rheological properties, glue line features, and it lowered the cost [168]. Water-resistance of water-washed cottonseed meal was improved by mixing with synthetic adhesive vinavil 2259 L from the classification of 'D1 - Inside application field condition' to 'D3 - Protected outside application field condition' in European standard EN204/205 [169].

The ability to use defatted cottonseed meal as a wood adhesive gives economic benefits to the wood adhesive industry for indoor applications. The process of water washing the cottonseed meal can enhance the water-resistance of the adhesive.

13 Geopolymer (Inorganic polymer) binders

A geopolymer binder for wood-based composites was developed based on pozzolanic by-products such as fly ash. Silica fume can be used as a replacement agent to extract geopolymer from aluminosilicate components such as fly ash and metakaolin to make the binder. The bonding shear strength was evaluated using 'Automated Bonding Evaluation System' ABES technique [170], [171]. The best shear strength of fly ash binders was found at the lowest press temperature and longest pressing time. Silica fume showed higher pozzolanic activity² than metakaolin, whereas fly ash showed lower strength compared to metakaolin. When investigating the use of increasing percentages of silica fume from 20% to 100%, a superior shear strength compared to conventional urea-formaldehyde resin and other geopolymer binders was achieved with the highest percentage studied (100%). Nevertheless, even at 20% of silica fume, the same bonding shear strength as for UF resin was achieved [170]. Geopolymer binding materials are inorganic, and they can be used as an alternative approach to the current formaldehyde emitting of current synthetic binders [172]. Geopolymers (inorganic polymers) are synthetic alkali aluminosilicate compositions produced by the reaction of an aluminosilicate powder with a highly concentrated alkali solution [173].

Alkaline activator (a mixture of a highly alkaline solution such as sodium silicate or potassium silicate) with NaOH or KOH is used to activate industrial by-products (silica fume or/and fly ash). Activated industrial by-products and high amount of silica and alumina from natural raw materials are used to manufacture geopolymer materials [174].

² A measure for the degree of reaction over time or the reaction rate between a pozzolan and Ca_2^+ or calcium hydroxide $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the presence of H_2O .

Alkali activation of fly ash has shown cementing characteristics such as smoothness, glassy state and shiny appearance [175].

Fly ash that can be taken from power plants is cheaper than pozzolanic materials. Fly ash can be divided into two groups according to the availability of calcium.

- ASTM class F - Low calcium fly ash. The preferred material.
- ASTM class C - high calcium fly ash. This interferes with the polymerisation and alters the geopolymer micro-structure.

Silica fume is a by-product of the ferro-silicon production industry and a highly effective pozzolanic material due to its extreme fineness and high silica content. So, its use in binders has shown to improve properties like compressive strength, bond strength and abrasion resistance. It has been shown that the interaction between geomaterial foam binder and wood achieves a desirable mechanical performance of resulted assemblies [176]. Geopolymer binders have demonstrated good adhesion properties between wood and earth bricks [177].

In conclusions, the addition of geopolymers into synthetic wood binders showed superior bond strengths as well as a reduction in the formaldehyde emission of the binder. Cementing characteristics of geopolymer can give smoothness, glassy state and shiny appearance to the final product of wood-based panels. Geopolymers are a by-product that can be sourced at very low cost and have shown the ability to even bond wood with earth bricks.

14 Hemicellulose wood adhesives

Wood is a complex mixture of large organic polymers, mainly cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. These three make up at least 95% by weight of dry wood. The remainder consists of fats, waxes, resins and simple phenols [178]. Xylan is a group of hemicellulose that can be sourced as a by-product in the pulp industry and recovered in large quantities from side streams of the agriculture and forestry industry [179]. Although xylan cannot be used directly as a wood adhesive, it has shown promising results as a high performance wood adhesive following the addition of dispersing agents such as poly(vinyl alcohol) or poly(vinylamine), and cross-linkers, such as glyoxal or hexa(methoxymethyl) melamine [180].

Olive kernel a lignocellulosic material that mainly contains cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin can have the ability to replace up to 15% of PF in a PF resin adhesives [181].

A four-stages squeeze extraction process was used to extract a wood adhesive from the bark of radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*). This four-stages extraction comprised: first two-stages of hot water extraction, a third stage of extraction at pH 8.3 (NaOH) followed by a fourth-stage extraction consisting in hot water washing. The resulting adhesive showed to produce type A-bond (fully weather and boil proof) in plywood [182], [183].

In conclusions, dispersing agents and cross-linkers are needed to prepare an improved hemicellulose wood adhesive. Nevertheless, several synthetic adhesives can be replaced by hemicellulose wood adhesives.

15 Laccase-Mediator

Laccases are multi-copper proteins (EC 1.10.3.2, p-diphenol: dioxygen oxidoreductases). They use molecular oxygen to oxidise various aromatic and non-aromatic compounds by a radical-catalysed reaction mechanism [184]. They are widely found in fungi [185]. Lignin, hemicellulose and carbohydrates are planet's own natural cross-linking agents [185]. Lignin contains many active functional groups such as phenolic hydroxyls, alcoholic hydroxyls and esters [186]. So, lignin behaves similarly to that of cement in reinforced concrete [187]. This causes wood to have tangential and radial direction mechanical strength [188].

Hemicellulose cross-linking effect can be achieved by the production of aldehydes, ketones, phenolic and other substances during hot pressing of lignocellulosic materials [189]. This causes to increase the medium density fibreboards (MDF) cross-link density [187].

Laccase increases catalytic oxidation of phenols, polyamines from lignin, as it has an oxidoreductase activity [190], [191]. During the catalytic oxidation, phenolic lignin forms phenoxy radicals which change into quinone compounds under different conditions. In a study a natural mediator (vanillin) and an artificial mediator (ABTS)³ were used by considering the steric hindrance in the reactions [187]. In this radical displacement reaction, the smaller molecular compounds (the mediators) oxidise the non-phenolic groups in lignin, without occupying the active site of the laccase, due to the steric hindrance [192], [193]. As a result of this, the catalytic efficiency of laccase increases and chemical and mechanical properties of the resulting MDF can be improved due to the availability of phenolic compounds of the active site of the laccase to react with the hydroxyls of wood cell walls [187]. After both types of mediator (vanillin and ABTS) were prepared, acetic acid/sodium acetate buffer solution was added to the laccase solution. Then they all were mixed, and weighted wood fibre was added. Oxygen was fed into the mixture for 55 min at 50°C. Chitosan (1.2%) was then added to the mixture as a water-proof agent. The mixture was hot-pressed at 10 MPa and 160°C for 512 seconds. Controlled samples were tested using deionised water as the solvent without adding laccase or mediator. Chitosan was not added into it before the hot-pressing [187]. The adhesives properties on wood of alkyl-chitosan exhibit better water-resistance compared to native chitosan [194]. Mechanical properties were examined after leaving the samples for 48 hours. The mechanical properties of MDF samples met the performance requirements of the 'People's Republic of China National Standard GB/T 11718 - 2009 (2009)'. The self-adhesive properties were achieved through esterification, hydrogen bonding, poly-condensation, coupling and Schiff base reaction, with coupling and poly-condensation being the most dominant [187].

The newly generated crystalline region in the cellulose has increased the mechanical strength of MDF during the reaction process. Degraded lignin moved to the MDF surface increasing the content of carboxyl groups during the hot-press process. As a result of this, high content of aldehyde groups was observed in the MDF interior [187]. Agricultural wastes and by-products of some industries are the main sources of bio-based wood

³ (2,2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid))

adhesives as well as some of the additives such as tannin. The pressing time can be reduced when tannin as an additive is used with laccase [195].

In conclusions, laccase has the ability to increase catalytic oxidation of phenols, polyamines and lignin which are the natural cross-linkers of plants. As a result of that, laccase can increase the mechanical and physical properties of wood-based panels.

16 Lignin Adhesive

Lignin is a large, amorphous, 3D polymer that can be produced by vascular terrestrial plants [196]. Lignin acts as an adhesive in the cell walls by holding cellulose fibres together [197], [198]. Hydroxy-cinnamyl alcohols, coniferyl alcohol and sinapyl alcohol, and minor amounts of coumaryl alcohol are the main building blocks of lignin [199]. They are phenolic, abundant, and low-cost materials which have lower reactivity towards formaldehyde or other aldehydes. Lignin and lignosulphonates can be mixed in small proportions with synthetic formaldehyde resins to reduce their cost while achieving similar mechanical and physical properties [7], [200], [201]. Lignin structures undergo rapid cross-linking reactions by forming esters and anhydrides [202]. Similar thermal properties of lignin were found in PF resins [203].

Exterior-grade structural finger joints and glulam based on soda bagasse lignin wood adhesive showed to satisfy the requirements of the relevant international specifications [204].

Lignin with glyoxal as a wood adhesive has achieved international standard specifications showing better values for internal bond (IB) strengths and sufficient press times compared to formaldehyde-based commercial wood adhesives [200].

Lignin modified with zinc and choline chloride-based deep-eutectic solvent (ChCl–ZnCl₂ DES) enhanced its reactivity towards the formation of resin adhesive. So, the sustainable integration of lignin in the wood adhesive industry can be further advanced [205]. The main disadvantages of lignin as an adhesive in the wood composite industry are:

1. Low reactivity → slow hardening → longer press curing times.
2. The concern of chemical variation in the feedstock due to the complex structure of lignin [196].

However, there is a successful system used today worldwide for high-density hard boards, which is called the 'Shen' system based on self-coagulation and cross-linking of lignin. This is done by a strong mineral acid in the presence of certain aluminium salt catalysts. However, this system has failed to produce MDF [6]. However, the pressing time was acceptably shorter when 1% of isocyanate (pMDI) was added to the board [206]. The cross-linking of desulphurised Kraft lignin with triethyl phosphate adhesion tested on wood has shown good hydrophobicity properties of the surface treated with lignin triethyl phosphate-based resin [207].

The addition of lignin into PF resins seemed to increase adhesive strength and decreases gel time [208]. Also, lignin-phenol-formaldehyde with coffee bean shelves has resulted as an enhanced adhesive [209], which required lower curing temperature [210].

Amounts of 65 wt.% of pre-methylated lignin, 10% - 15% of synthetic phenolic formaldehyde resin and 20% - 25% of pMDI were used as a wood adhesive. This gave the fastest pressing time in the industry due to high cross-link density of formation of methylene and urethane bridge [6], [211].

Lignin isolated from Kenaf *Hibiscus cannabinus* via soda and Kraft pulping and modified with soda lignin-phenol-glyoxal showed higher tensile strength and internal bonding stress at 72.08 MPa and 53.83 N/mm² respectively compared to that of PF [212].

Tannin/hexamine with glyoxylated lignin as a wood adhesive satisfied the values required by the European standards [213]. It was found that up to 50% of phenol can be replaced by bagasse lignin to give lignin phenol formaldehyde wood adhesive with better bonding strength in comparison to a control phenol formaldehyde wood adhesive [214].

In addition, 50% glyoxalated alfa lignin and 50% of Aleppo Pine tannins yielded a good internal bond strength of 0.45 MPa for one-layer wood panels satisfying relevant international standard specifications for interior-grade wood panels [215]. Lignin can be pre-glyoxalated in a reactor to get glyoxalated lignin⁴. That can then be mixed with tannin and pMDI eliminating the need for any formaldehyde or formaldehyde-based resins. Wheat straw organosolv lignin has been applied the above technology. It showed to satisfy requirements for industrially significant pressing time. The mechanism of copolymerisation and hardening is shown in Figure 6[7].

Figure 6 : Schematic path of the simultaneous corrections of glyoxalated lignin with the tannin/hexamine adhesive system [7].

Lignin can react with hexamethylene diamine to form hard, condensed solids between the temperature of 100°C and 180°C showing wood adhesive properties [216].

⁴ glyoxal is a non-toxic and non-volatile aldehyde.

Enzymatic hydrolysis lignin derived from bioethanol with PF gives comparable properties to those of commercial wood adhesive [217].

Alkali-treated Moroccan sugar cane bagasse lignin was used to replace 30% of the PF resins utilised to bond plywood panels satisfying relevant international standard specifications for interior-grade panels [218].

Lignocellulosic ethanol residue is a by-product of lignocellulosic ethanol production and rich in activated lignin and usually treated as waste. The thermal stability of lignocellulosic ethanol residue modified PF adhesives was better than that of PF adhesive in the initial thermal degradation [219].

Fibreboards containing 15% acid-washed Kraft lignin have indicated good mechanical and water-resistance properties that fully satisfied the relevant standards specifications [220]. Addition of hyperbranched poly (amine-ester) to tannin adhesive was able to improve the water-resistance of glyoxalated Kraft lignin resin [221]. Higher bonding strength and water-resistance were obtained by using a chitosan-lignin wood adhesive, which was inexpensive and environmentally friendly [222].

In conclusions, lignin in virgin wood behaves as a natural binder of wood cell walls linking cellulose fibres together. So, lignin as a complex organic polymer, has the ability to bond one wood cell to another. The ability of copolymerisation of lignin with other polymers can give added advantages to the adhesive properties of lignin. Lignin is the second most abundant biopolymer; it is inexpensive and the ability to be developed into a wood adhesive to an industrial scale is viable.

17 Nanoparticle Modification of Polymers and Soy-based Adhesives

Nanoparticle reinforcement in polymers and adhesives is very effective in improving their performance. Multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) was used to reinforce soy-based polyurethane (PU) foam and then compressive, flexural, and tensile properties were compared with neat polyurethane foam. The properties of MWCNTs-PU foam were improved by 24%, 30% and 34% respectively [223]. Aligned MWCNTs (compared to the unaligned MWCNTs) were successfully able to prevent crack development. As a result of that, the tensile strength increased. Soy-based polyol and polymeric diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI) were used to make polyurethane foam. Mechanical properties and thermal stability were improved by incorporating Nanoclay Cloisite[®] 30B [224]. By adding nanoclay (0.5% wt.) to the soy-based polyurethane, the mechanical properties were increased by 22% to 98%. The smaller cell size of foam composites causes an impressive increase in impressive strength and modulus of Nanoclay soy-based polyurethane foams [225].

Although bio-nano-adhesives obtained by dispersing montmorillonite clay into a soy protein concentrate matrix showed better adhesive performance to the wood material, the wet adhesion of the nanocomposites had similar values of the adhesive without nanoparticles [226]. The addition of nanoclay sodium-montmorillonite into urea-lignin-formaldehyde resin showed to increase the viscosity by 1.5% and free formaldehyde and gel time of the resin were reduced [227]. Nanoclay can efficiently be mixed with polyvinyl acetate by using ultrasonication technique [228].

Biological resistance of wood-composites against wood-deteriorating fungi (fungi, insects and termites, and marine borers) was improved by adding nano-metals and nano-minerals. In addition to that, the thermal conductivity coefficient of the wood composite mats was increased by adding highly thermal conductive nano-metals and nano-wollastonite. As a result of that, the hot-pressing time, physical and mechanical properties were improved [229]. Nano TiO₂ with natural castor oil-based polyurethane adhesives exhibited improved water-resistance compared with castor polyurethane itself [230]. Nano-silver impregnated wood panels showed a lower amount of water absorption and an insignificant increase in thickness swelling. The impregnated panels showed a better mechanical property compared to the physical properties [231]. However, both physical and mechanical properties were increased by adding 100 ml/kg and 150 ml/kg nanocopper, which also reduced the hot press time by 5.7% and 3.4% respectively [232].

Water impermeability of MDF was improved by adding zycosil nanoparticles [233]. Wollastonite nanofibers demonstrated the ability to increase the thermal conductivity by 11.5% causing a better curing of the resin in the core section of MDF mat [234].

Penetration of water and vapour into a wood-composite matrix was prevented by adding silane nanoparticle [235]. Higher effectiveness of preservatives and fire-retardants, ultimately increasing the service life were obtained by impregnating the wood with aqueous nanomaterials, which increased the permeability of solid wood [236].

Nano-silver showed fire-retarding properties in solid woods [237]. In general, nanomaterials can have the ability to improve e properties of wood-based panels and to help in overcoming some of their shortcomings [238].

Nanomaterial reinforced canola protein adhesives showed improved water-resistance and adhesion strength. In fact, hydrophilic bentonite, surface modified nanoclay (SM-MMT), graphite oxide, and nanocrystalline cellulose were exfoliated using solution intercalation method. While the addition of SM-MMT increased the dry, wet and soaked strengths, bentonite significantly increased only the dry strength [239]. Nanomaterial reinforcement gave added value to canola protein isolated adhesives by improving their water-resistance. However, new research studies are needed to shorter the curing time of canola protein isolated adhesives.

In conclusions, addition of nanomaterials into a wood adhesive resin can:

1. prevent cracks development;
2. reduce penetration of water and vapour into wood composite;
3. reduce hot press time;
4. improve mechanical and physical properties;
5. improve biological resistance against wood-deteriorating fungi of wood composites.

18 Polyvinyl acetate wood adhesives

Polyvinyl acetate (PVA)-based adhesives are ready-to-use thermoplastic resins that set rapidly at room temperature. Due to the high dry strength, low clamping pressure, and competitive cost, PVA adhesives are widely used in the furniture industry [240]. PVA adhesives can resist microorganisms' attacks. In addition to PVA, polyvinyl formal, and polyvinyl butyral are used to bond metals or plastics to wood [241].

PVA is a non-toxic, colourless thermoplastic adhesive made by polymerised vinyl acetate [242]. PVA with 15% of melamine-formaldehyde has shown better thermal stability than when it was used purely as a wood adhesive. Wood joints' strength in wet conditions and at elevated temperature were improved by adding a small amount of melamine urea formaldehyde or melamine formaldehyde into PVA [243].

PVA has been used as wood adhesive to bond oriental beech in order to investigate the effect of the amount of adhesive, pressing pressure, and pressing time on bonding strength [244]. Vitamin C was introduced as the reduction agent as an alternative to sodium formaldehyde sulfoxylate to enhance the adhesive properties of PVA D3⁵ and also to minimise formaldehyde emission [245].

The tensile strength was doubled, and the stiffness was increased by 50% by adding 0.1 vol% of graphene into PVA wood adhesive [246]. The bonding performance of environmentally friendly PVA emulsion adhesive can further be improved by copolymerising with vinyl acetate and butyl acrylate monomers [247]. PVA is also capable of attacking microorganisms in wood [241]. Drying oil modified PVA showed improved water and solvent resistance [248]. Improved water and moisture resistance was also achieved when aluminium salt was added to PVA [249].

PVA can also be used as a non-formaldehyde emitting wood adhesive directly or when blended with other adhesives. It can also minimise the formaldehyde emission when blended with formaldehyde-based wood adhesives.

19 Starch-based wood adhesives

Starch is a polysaccharide that can be obtained from roots, stalks, and seeds of staple crops⁶. It is a biodegradable, inexpensive, easily accessible, renewable, and readily available biopolymer that can be used as a wood adhesive [250]–[252]. The building blocks of starch are polymers of the six-carbon sugar D-glucose units consisting of two major bio-macromolecules amylose and amylopectin [253]. Amylose has the ability to form a gel when the starch granule is cooked. Gel formation is the result of the retrogradation (re-association) of solubilised starch polymers after cooking [254]–[257].

⁵ Protected outside application field condition PVA

⁶ rice, corn, wheat, tapioca and potato

High amylose starch-based wood adhesive with the addition of sucrose fatty acid esters 6% (w/w, of total amount of dry starch) was shown to be able to improve its dry and wet bonding strengths, storage stability and the adhesive mobility [258]. Amylopectin is a branched polymer that has a much higher molecular weight than amylose [259].

Starch-based bio-polymer system has advantages of low brittleness, low formaldehyde emission (when mixed with UF), and ability to reduce water adsorption [260]. The bonding strength and water-resistance of particleboard were improved significantly by adding isocyanates to starch adhesive and UF showing very low formaldehyde emission [261].

Epichlorohydrin-modified oil palm starch adhesive was used to make particleboard using rubberwood particles. Apart from water-resistance, the mechanical and physical properties of the resulting particleboards were able to meet the minimum required strength as stated in Japanese Industrial Standards (JIS A 5908: Particleboards) [262]. Particleboards made of nonmodified oil palm starch adhesive met all mechanical properties but none of the physical properties such as water-resistance according to JIS [263]. However, carboxy-methyl starch-based adhesive which has hydrophilicity and stability during freezing and thawing was manufactured in order to enhance water-resistance [264]. Carboxymethyl starch (prepared by chemically modifying oil palm trunk starch with phosphoryl chloride) as a wood binder with rubberwood has shown better mechanical and physical properties compared to the panels bonded with native starch [66].

Addition of 1.5% – 2% (w/w of total amount of dry starch) of sodium dodecyl sulphate into starch-based wood adhesive resulted in significantly enhanced resin mobility and storage stability, although with a slight deterioration in the shear strength [265].

Corn-starch and tannin mixed wood adhesive has shown excellent structural stability according to European norm, EN 312 (2004) [266]. Plywood panels bonded with a ratio of corn starch : quebracho tannin : PF resins of 15:5:80, (w/w/w) exhibited better mechanical properties than plywood panels bonded with commercial PF [267]. Wood adhesive made by crosslinking corn-starch and PVA with hexamethoxy-methylmelamine has shown excellent mechanical properties comparable to many of the commercially available UF plywood adhesives used for interior applications [268]. Starch-based wood adhesive cross-linked with γ -methacryloxypropyl trimethoxy silane has exhibited enhanced shear strength and storage stability showing improved apparent viscosity and less pseudo-plastic behaviour [269].

The cost of starch and PVA-based cross-linked wood adhesives is lower or equivalent to conventional phenolic resins used as wood adhesives [270].

Acid hydrolysis of starch-based wood adhesive exhibited the optimal shear strengths of 6.65 MPa in the dry state and 3.6 MPa in the wet state with the improvement due to the grafting reaction and reduced steric hindrance [271].

Particleboard panels were manufactured using 15% corn starch-modified with glutaraldehyde and tested. The modulus of rupture and the internal bond strength of the panels met JIS [272].

In another study, starch-based polyvinyl acetate wood adhesive was made using graft copolymerisation of mixed grafting monomers vinyl acetate and butyl acrylate onto

grafting skeleton of corn starch. The resulting wood products showed to satisfy the national standard HG/T2727 - 95 especially with their compressive shear strength [273]. Corn-starch adhesives behave as pseudo-plastic fluids [274].

A graft-copolymerised high-performance starch-based wood adhesive prepared using H_2O_2 , a silane coupling agent and an olefin monomer as an oxidant, cross-linking agent and comonomer respectively, has shown enhanced thermal stability, an increased bonding strength and enhanced water-resistance [275].

Graft copolymerisation of vinyl acetate monomer onto corn-starch in aqueous solution was developed with a system based on potassium persulphate/acetone sodium bisulphite and higher shear strength was achieved [276]. Improved bonding performances were seen with the addition of sodium dodecyl sulphate to starch wood-based adhesive [277]. High amylose starch-based wood adhesive with sodium dodecyl sulphate as an effective emulsifier increased the storage properties and bonding performance of wood adhesive in a low-temperature environment [278]. It has also been shown that urea 15% (w/w) can be used as an effective additive for improving storage properties of starch-based wood adhesive in a low-temperature environment [279].

Addition of montmorillonite to the starch-based wood adhesive was able to improve its overall performance [280]. A urea-oxidised starch wood adhesive also showed an excellent overall performance when a urea content of 50% (w/w, of dry starch basis) and 5.0% (w/w, of dry starch basis) $KMnO_4$ as the oxidiser, were added to the adhesive [281].

Starch nanoparticles show better adhesive properties than starch microparticles [282]. The addition of silica nanoparticles (10%) into reinforced starch-based wood adhesive resulted in an increase of bonding strength by 50.1% in the dry state and 84.0% in wet state, and an increase in water-resistance increased by 20.2% [283].

Polyurethane adhesives, were synthesised from potato starch and natural oils by a transesterification reaction, were found superior to the commercially available wood adhesive [284].

Another starch-based wood adhesive was prepared using dry esterification. After esterification, whereas the crystal structure types of native starch have not changed, the thermal stability had decreased, and a more uniform distribution of adhesive at the bonding interface was achieved [285].

Very good internal bond strength and thickness swelling values were found when low-density particleboards were made using an adhesive system based on sour cassava starch [286]. Organic siloxane-modified starch-based wood adhesive via oxidised cassava starch and then grafted copolymerisation with acrylamide, butyl acrylate monomer, and vinyltriisopropoxysilane has shown to increase the bonding strength and water-resistance. This was due to the starch-based adhesive multi-alkoxy silane reacting with the hydroxyl groups of the starch molecules and the two being crosslinked in the emulsion. Addition of organic siloxane increased the bonding strength and water-resistance of cassava starch-based wood adhesive by reducing the content of the hydroxyl groups on the starch molecules [287].

Starch-based wood adhesive graft copolymerised with vinyl acetate at $90^\circ C$ showed the improved performance [288]. Performance of a high starch content wood adhesive can

also be enhanced by combining lauryl sodium sulphate with alkylphenol ethoxylates [289].

In conclusions, most of the modified starch-based wood adhesives satisfy international requirements on mechanical properties as well as physical properties such as water-resistance. The mobility and storage stability of starch-based adhesives can be enhanced by adding sodium dodecyl sulphate, sucrose fatty acid esters and urea. Smaller starch particles showed to lead to better adhesive properties. Addition of nanoparticles into starch-based adhesives increased bonding strength as well as water-resistance.

20 Tannins Adhesive

Tannins can be sourced from wood, leaves, bark and plant fruits [2] and have been used industrially for five decades as an alternative to petroleum-derived phenolic resin for interior and exterior wood panels [290]. They are polyhydroxyphenols, and soluble in water, alcohols, and acetone [291]. Black wattle (*Acacia mearnsii*) bark was used to extract wattle tannin and used as a wood adhesive in Australia in the 1960s [292].

According to the phenolic nature of tannins, they can be classified into two groups as hydrolysable tannins and condensed tannins (90% of the total world production of commercial tannins) [196]. Phenolic composition of sumac root barks is higher in condensed tannins than in hydrolysable tannins [293]. Similarly, Tunisian Aleppo pine barks are richer in condensed tannins than in hydrolysable tannins [294].

Tannins can be used as exterior grade weather-resistant wood adhesives cross-linked with formaldehyde [7]. As most phenolic adhesives, tannin-based adhesives emits formaldehyde at very low levels [13]. Chestnut (*Castanea sativa*) shell tannin extracts mixed with tris(hydroxymethyl)nitromethane, glyoxal and hexamine used as hardeners showed better results than formaldehyde-free wood adhesive [295]–[297]. Tannin-phenol-formaldehyde adhesive cures faster than the commercial phenol-formaldehyde adhesive, which leads to shorter press time and therefore to an increase in productivity [298] and the same result was obtained with phenol-urea-formaldehyde-tannin too [299].

Tannins exhibit a similar reactive potential as phenols due to the phenolic type subunits contained in them. This increases the reactivity towards formaldehyde of 10 to 50 times due to the increase in hydroxyl substitutions. Formaldehyde reacts with tannin the same as it reacts with phenol forming methylene bridges. This causes a noticeable improvement in water and weather resistance [300]. Bio composites made with pre-treated flax and tannin have shown to be highly resistant to mould growth [301]. Commercial industrial particleboard panels made using either melamine-formaldehyde or tannin paraformaldehyde were exposed to the weather at 1500 m of altitude with high UV exposure for 15 years. Significant damages were observed to the edges of the melamine-formaldehyde particleboard panels, while tannin para-formaldehyde panels remain unchanged [196].

A phenol-tannin-formaldehyde resin prepared using 50% tannins from acorns of valonia oak and phenol-formaldehyde resins showed comparable performance to PF only resins [302]. Modified onion skin tannin extracts resins cured at ambient conditions satisfied the strength and durability requirements of the International Standards Organisations [303].

Purified pine bark tannins and food-grade, non-toxic, slow-reacting lignin-derived aldehydes were used for the preparation of adhesives capable of bonding wood particleboards. The resulting adhesives satisfied the relevant European standards [304].

20.1 Tannin-Hexamethylenediamine (Hexamine) adhesive

Hexamine (C₆H₁₂N₄) is one of the most common formaldehyde scavengers used in wood processing industries to minimise formaldehyde emissions from wood-based panels [305]. Hexamine is considered as non-formaldehyde-yielding compound and used as a hardener in tannin-based adhesives [6]. Tannin-hexamine⁷ adhesives, with hexamine being a non-formaldehyde yielding compound, are cheaper and commercially available. They emit extremely low formaldehyde [7]. The main decomposition and re-composition mechanism of hexamine rather proceeds through reactive intermediates than directly forming formaldehyde. The use of hexamine as a hardener of tannin and tannin-hexamine adhesives makes them environmentally friendly. The formaldehyde emissions when measured in a chamber have proven to be so low to be limited exclusively to what is generated by the wood itself. So, wood panels made with such type of adhesives are truly an E0⁸ panel [7]. Steam injection presses have shown better results for 'exterior grade boards' using tannin-hexamine adhesives. Hexamine is a reactive cross-linker that has also been used with corn flour-mimosa tannin-based adhesives (50:50), with resulting wood products showing good mechanical properties [306]. The chemical reaction between hexamine and tannins is shown in reaction 2. The mass proportion of tannin powder and hexamine ground was 5:1 [307].

Where, $n = 3 - m$,

Zinc salt has been used as catalysts in tannins and hexamine-based adhesives for better results and faster press time [7]. Resin mixtures of tannin and hexamine have been tested according to Japanese standards, JIS A 5908, and results are reported in Table 3. [308].

⁷ hexamine is a non-formaldehyde-yielding compound

⁸ Wood-based panel with no emission of formaldehyde whatsoever

Table 3 : The results of thick laboratory panels bonded with Tanzanian mimosa tannin and hexamine. The total duration of steam injection was 60 seconds [308].

Tannin type	Hexamine (%)	pH	Resin load (%)	Board thickness (mm)	Press time (sec)	Board density (kg/m ³)	Dry strength (Mpa)	IB	IB 4h boil (Mpa)	24h cold water swelling (%)	FE (mg/L)
Mimosa-O	5	7	7	40	330	0.75	0.37			17.1	0.0
	5	8	7	40	330	0.75	0.57			14.4	0.0
	5	9	7	40	330	0.75	0.58			14.1	0.0
	5	10	7	40	330	0.74	0.73			12.8	0.0
Mimosa-T	5	10	7	25	380	0.85	0.95			12.0	0.0
	10	10	7	25	380	0.84	0.71			13.8	0.0
	15	10	7	25	380	0.81	0.78			15.0	0.0
	5	10	5	25	380	0.85	0.83	0.06		15.3	0.0
	5	10	7	25	380	0.83	0.82	0.07		12.0	0.0
	5	10	5	25	380	0.85	0.98	0.09		10.0	0.0
	5	10	7	40	380	0.75	0.78			12.0	0.0
Require							≥ 0.30			≤ 12.00	≤ 0.3

Corn-starch-tannin with hexamine as a wood adhesive resin was used to make plywood panels in order to compare the mechanical properties such as modulus of rupture (MOR), modulus of elasticity (MOE), dry tension strength, veneer failure and formaldehyde emission with those of commercial phenol formaldehyde [309]. The corn-starch-tannin adhesive substituted by hexamine showed comparatively better mechanical properties able to meet the international standard specifications [309] as shown in Table 4. Equal proportions of tannin/hexamine and non-purified glyoxalated lignin formulate on showed the dry IB strength of 0.52 ± 0.05 MPa⁹ and dry tensile strength of 1.2 ± 0.20 MPa¹⁰ [310], [311].

Table 4 : MOR, MOE, dry tensile strength and formaldehyde emission results for plywood panels prepared with the experimental adhesive compared to results obtained with a phenol-formaldehyde resin and with wood alone. Six replicates of each adhesive. SD: Standard deviation [309].

Adhesives	MOR, MPa Mean \pm SD	MOE, MPa Mean \pm SD	Dry tension strength, MPa Mean \pm SD	Veneer Failure (%)	FE, mg/m ² /h
Commercial phenol-formaldehyde	48 \pm 6.14	3310 \pm 866	2.07 \pm 0.04	> 95	2.62 \pm 0.19
Corn-starch-tannin	42 \pm 3.77	3122 \pm 544	1.86 \pm 0.22	> 80	0.20 \pm 0.08
Wood only control	-	-	-	-	0.17 \pm 0.04

20.2 Hardening by tannin autocondensation

Tannin autocondensation is done in the absence of aldehydes [312] and is an acid-catalysed oxidative condensation. Although the viscosity increases in the reaction, gelling does not generally occur. However, in the presence of a small amount of

⁹ European Norm EN 314-2 requirement is ≥ 0.35

¹⁰ EN 314-2 requirements is ≥ 1.0

dissolved silica catalyst and other catalysts and on a lignocellulosic surface, gelling takes place [6].

The dry internal bond (IB) strength of interior particleboards prepared using Pecan and Pine tannins was 0.8 MPa when pH was 13 satisfying German industrial standards (DIN 68763) requirements. The IB requirement for DIN 68763 is 0.35 MPa or above. Nevertheless, Mimosa and Quebracho tannin could not achieve this result [312].

Dry strength of wood panels bonded with tannins was increased with autocondensation reactions. However, the exterior grade performance of the panels remained unchanged as it mainly depends on poly-condensation reactions with aldehydes rather than autocondensation reactions [7].

Tannin autocondensation was shown to increase by adding boric acid into induced quebracho tannin. This decreased the pressing time and cure temperature increasing the modulus of elasticity [313].

Particleboards bonded with aningre (*Aningeria spp.*) tannin adhesives showed to satisfy the particleboard dry IB strength requirements of the standard (Norm NF EN 312-2: 1996) for general purposes panels used in dry environments [314].

Shear refinement (290 rpm and 5 min, optimal conditions) was done for corn starch–mimosa tannin wood adhesives to reduce the viscosity (from 100,000 P a s to 458 P a s) while mechanical properties remained same [315].

A polenta corn-starch-mimosa tannin-UF (10:4:86; mass ratios) adhesive mixture exhibited better mechanical properties and less formaldehyde emission than boards made from commercial UF resins [315].

Extraction of condensed tannins from grape pomace was tested using a mixture of water-sodium hydroxide solutions at 120°C. Promising properties for wood adhesive applications were obtained by using 10% of NaOH [316], [317]. Similar results were obtained with 5% of NaOH extract from maritime pine *Pinus pinaster* [318]. Combination of 70% tannin, 21% pMDI and 9% of glyoxal showed dry IB strength of 0.6 MPa with a low formaldehyde emission of 0.6 mg/100g [319].

Condensed tannins such as wattle (Mimosa) extract could partially be modified through hydrolysis of a benzyl ether link and the consequent opening of the flavonoid heterocyclic ring, through sulphitation. These sulphited tannin adhesives demonstrated to be useful in applications, such as particleboards manufacture [320].

Barbatimao tannin adhesive as a substitute for PF during plywood production had a significant effect on the water absorption, wet shear strength, and modulus of perpendicular elasticity [25]. In another study, a novel wood adhesive was made by mixing procyanidin-type condensed tannin and polyethylenimine [321].

In conclusions, the advantage of using tannins as a bio-based adhesive is that they can be cross-linked by formaldehyde in a polycondensation reaction in order to get exterior grade weather-resistant wood adhesives. Resins made by adding 50% of tannins into PF have shown comparable performance to PF only resins. This can minimise cost and formaldehyde emissions. The combination of tannins and hexamine showed improved performance as a nontoxic wood adhesive.

21 Unsaturated oil adhesives

Unsaturated vegetable oils consist of at least one double bond. So, they can be used as wood and wood composite adhesives by oxidising the double bonds followed by their carbonation [322]. Resins can be prepared by using linseed oil, which can be used as a wood adhesive or surface-coating material [323]. Epoxidation of linseed oil double bonds followed by cross-linking with a cyclic polycarboxylic acid anhydride builds up its molecular weight by adding carboxylic groups into it. These can then react with the hydroxy groups of wood cell walls by adjoining one wood cell to another [7]. Cross-linking can be varied by the addition of specialised catalysts and preparing the samples at a range of temperatures (120°C - 180°C) and the resulting wood products showed high water tolerance. Their high costs and the long pressing time required are the main disadvantages of linseed oil wood adhesive [324].

On the other hand, it has been shown that hydroxyl fatty acid of oilseed crop has great potential application in adhesives [325]. Nevertheless, these resins have major disadvantages in the wood adhesive industry such as slow hot-pressing time, relative high prices and unfavourable environmental profile [7].

Bio-resins based on soybean oils were developed as a replacement of polyester resins. These liquid bio-resins were obtained from plant and animal triglycerides by functionalising the triglyceride with chemical groups¹¹ that can make them polymerizable. Soy oil-based resins have a strong affinity for natural fibres, and this could make them a better fibre-matrix interface as determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). These resins can be considered as a candidate replacement for phenol-formaldehyde, urethane, and other petroleum-based binders in particleboard, MDF, oriented strand board (OSB), etc [326].

Cashew nutshell liquid consists mainly of cardanol. It has phenolic nuclei and an unsaturated fatty acid chain as shown in Figure 7.

¹¹ epoxy, carboxyl, hydroxyl, vinyl, amine

Figure 7 : Chemical structure of cardanol.

So, cardanol's dual nature implies a potential as natural raw material for water-resistant resins and polymers. Double bonds in the chain can be used to form hardened networks.

Nevertheless, the modifications of the alkenyl chain need several reaction steps, which are too expensive for the commercial wood adhesive industry [7].

Unsaturated oil such as sunflower oil is a commonly available material. Following ozonolysis and reduction of sunflower oil and after the co-reaction of the obtained non-volatile long-chain aldehyde with flavonoid tannins from radiata pine (*Pinus radiata*), the resulting adhesive was used to make particleboards, which showed to contain a relatively low amount of formaldehyde [327]. Ozonolysis and reduction of soybean oil produced aldehyde oil, malonaldehyde, capraldehyde and pelargonaldehyde, which can be used as wood adhesives [328].

Urea Formaldehyde and acrylic-epoxidised soy oil (ASEO) were used to make wheat straw particleboard with different resin content levels and different pressing times. The mechanical and physical properties of ASEO-bonded particle boards showed better results than UF-bonded boards, especially in internal bonding and thickness swelling [329].

Jatropha oil is a non-edible oil and has 78.5% unsaturated fatty acids and was used to make Jatropha oil-based polyurethane wood adhesive. It has shown better shear strength, and its response to hot water, acid, and alkali was superior compared to palm oil-based wood adhesives [330]. Wood adhesives prepared from softwood bark residues pyrolysis oil developed for exterior-grade oriented strand board (OSB) have shown significantly improved internal bond strength and thickness swelling [331].

In conclusions, ozonolysis and reduction of unsaturated long-chain oils can produce aldehyde oils. However, the major issues with unsaturated oil-based adhesives are slow hot-press time, high costs of oil and unfavourable environmental profile.

22 Seed meal (seed flour) wood adhesive

Finely grounded untreated seed meals (defatted meals), water-washed meals and their protein isolate can be used as a wood adhesive [332]. However, the adhesive viscosity and the hydrodynamic volume of its components should be small enough for the adhesive to be able to penetrate wood. Although soy flour is economically viable, its adhesive strength is much lower than that of commercial soy protein isolate [333]. Water washing can enrich the protein content by 12% to 25% in the washed meal of water-insoluble fraction [334]. Water washed or phosphate buffer washed cottonseed meals has shown better water-resistance than cottonseed protein isolate. This is a low-cost and environmentally friendly protein-based adhesive, which does not incorporate corrosive alkali and acid solutions for the extraction of its protein isolate [335]. Tung oil has shown to increase the adhesive strength of water washed cottonseed meal and of its protein isolate by 19.9% and 21.1%, respectively. In addition to that, the water-resistances were increased by 46.6% and 41.3%, respectively [336].

The increase in the percentage of mechanical properties of protein isolate from a water washed meal is lower when compared with the economic effort that must be made to produce protein isolate from the defatted meal. Usage of water washed seed meals as wood adhesive gives economic benefits compared to protein isolates.

23 Miscellaneous Wood Adhesive

PF, pMDI, epoxy and starch resin/adhesive made by blending or synthesising bio-oil have been used to manufacture plywood, OSB, particleboard and flakeboard [337]. Glyoxal-monomethylol urea prepared by synthesising the non-volatile and non-toxic aldehyde glyoxal and monomethylol urea was used to make plywood panels. The results showed the dry shear strength of 0.90 MPa satisfying the Chinese National Standard GB/T 9846.3-2004 [338].

Another study showed that the addition of 20% to 30% of animal glue into melamine-formaldehyde adhesives does not deteriorates the mechanical properties of wood-based composites. This can lower the cost of resin adhesive [339].

Locust bean gum, guar gum, xanthan gum and tamarind gum were used as wood adhesives. The gum dispersion in commercial PVA proved that it can be used as a binder for wood adhesives [340].

Amazonic White Pitch (*Protium heptaphyllum*) investigated as an environmentally friendly wood adhesive showed a shear strength higher than the tensile strength [341].

An adhesive made using peanut meal, sodium dodecyl sulphate and glycol diglycidyl ether fulfilled the requirements for interior used plywood [342].

Pea (*Pisum sativum L.*) protein as a valid alternative to soy proteins resulted to be a wood adhesive with improved water-resistance when an additive was included in the mixture [86]. Vanillin is a bio-based epoxy, which showed properties close to the current Bisphenol A-based industrial adhesive [343].

In conclusions, different types of biopolymers can be used as wood adhesive directly or when blended with other wood adhesives. Consideration of their chemistry and changing the physical parameters during the process of manufacturing can deliver better performing wood-based panels.

24 Conclusion and future perspectives

Table 5 : Non-toxic, bio-based wood adhesive with potential advantages and blendability.

Adhesive	Potential advantage	Can be blended with
Lignin	Abundant and low cost [7], [201], [344]	Tannin [7], [215], glyoxal [221], [344], PF [218], pMDI [6], [7], Hexamine [7].
Tannin	Weather-resistant [7]	Glyoxal, hexamine [295]–[297], PF [25], [298], corn-starch [309], phenol-urea-formaldehyde [299].
Canola protein	Second largest oilseed crop product [87][88]	Hydrophilic bentonite, surface modified nanoclay [239].
Wheat gluten	Abundant, inexpensive [42].	Alkaline solutions [46], UF [48].
Cotton-seed protein	Higher shear strength [160]	Starch, xylan, cellulose [345], guanidine hydrochloride GuHCl, sodium dodecyl sulfonate, urea, and alkali [165].
Soy-based	Low cost [93]	Maleic anhydride, polyethylemine [99], CaCO ₃ [100], lignin [346], blood, casein [103], glyoxalated lignin, tannin [105], hydroxymethyl phenol [110], POCl ₃ , [121] polyethyleneimine, NaOH [116], sodium sulfite and sodium dodecyl sulfate [118], epichlorohydrin ammonium hydroxide, NaOH [123].
Geopolymer	Pozzolanic by-product	Silica fume [170].
Unsaturated oil	Good for exterior-grade applications [331]	UF and acrylic-epoxidised soy oil [329].
Xylan	By-product in pulp industry [179]	Poly(vinyl alcohol), poly(vinylamine), glyoxal, hexa(methoxymethyl) melamine [180].
Starch	Readily available [250]–[252]	Sucrose fatty acid esters [258], sodium dodecyl sulphate [265], quebracho tannin, PF resins [267], polyvinyl alcohol with hexamethoxy-methylmelamine [268], γ -Methacryloxypropyl trimethoxy silane [269], H ₂ O ₂ , a silane coupling agent and an olefin monomer [275], grafting monomers vinyl acetate [273], glutardialdehyde [272], urea [279], silica nanoparticles [283], polyurethane [284], acrylamide, butyl acrylate monomer, and vinyltriisopropoxysilane [287], lauryl sodium sulphate with alkylphenol ethoxylates [289].

This paper has reviewed the potential non-toxic and/or bio-based wood adhesives that can be used directly or in combination with synthetic adhesives in order to achieve

mechanical and physical properties that either satisfy the international standards or show performance similar to the industrially used reference adhesives, such as urea-formaldehyde. In addition to that, the usage of bio-based wood adhesives either reduces or eliminates the toxic formaldehyde emission satisfying the formaldehyde emission requirement of the international standards. This allows opportunities for particleboard manufacturer to re-manufacture the panels over and over again. Although some synthetic wood adhesives such as pMDI that do not emit formaldehyde show better performance than the formaldehyde-based ones, they are economically not viable in the industrial scale.

While soy-based wood adhesives are the major constituent of the bio-based wood adhesive sector and are economically viable, their physical properties need to be improved. Several ongoing research studies are currently focusing on the enhancement of the water-resistance of soy-based wood adhesive.

The main advantage of bio-based wood adhesives is that they can be used as a wood adhesive directly or blended with other bio-based or synthetic wood adhesives to enhance mechanical and/or physical properties of wood panels. Such hybrid adhesive formulations are much easier to adapt to the current wood adhesive manufacturing lines in the wood panel industries. The non-toxic adhesives, mentioned in this manuscript, with their potential advantages and blendabilities are shown in Table 5.

24.1 Future challenges and perspectives

In general, the interaction between different types of biopolymers and other compounds that can be blended to make adhesives can contribute to the adhesive forces of the resulting resins. As a result of this, future research studies should focus on the possibilities of adding chemical modifications to innovative bio-based resins on the basis of their chemical structures. In addition to the chemical structures, other factors such as thermal degradation and ability of making mechanical interlockings play a major role in bonding of wood. Nanometre length scale wood adhesive interactions should also be considered when mechanical interlocking is concerned [347].

Formaldehyde emissions of synthetic adhesives can be minimised down to the international standards by incorporating bio-based adhesives into them without degrading physical and mechanical properties of the resulted wood-based panels. This is mostly due to the bio-based wood adhesives behaving as formaldehyde scavengers. Pizzi et al 2013 [348] have classified future challenges of bio-based wood adhesive into four sections.

1. Performance and application compared to synthetic adhesives,
2. Cost compared to synthetic adhesives,
3. Supply of raw materials,
4. Natural resistance to change and resistance to destroy the existing synthetic wood adhesive market.

New research is also needed to: i) reduce the press time; ii) increase the water and moisture Resistance; iii), find cheaper raw materials and alternative products; iv) recycle and reuse and reduce the emissions in hybrid wood adhesive systems [348].

Identification of the type of the protein which gives the best adhesive properties has not been discovered yet. Although the cost of the plant seed meals is low, extracting protein isolate from them is expensive. The adhesive properties of water washed and/or buffer washed plant seed meal fractions can be compared with that of protein isolate of the same plant seed. It will also be necessary to find alternatives to using human consumable plant products as bio-based wood adhesive when future global food security is concerned [349].

Another issue identified is that a noticeable bio-based adhesive strength loss was seen after 12 months of storage [350]. New research studies are needed to overcome the durability problems of bio-based adhesives and a systematic approach is needed to transfer bio-based adhesive to the commercially available production lines [349].

Ultimately, the end user of wood-based panels should be satisfied with the cost, quality, durability and the desired quantity. In order to do that, a sustainable manufacturing approach that can compete with the existing market should be implemented.

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